

Catalytic Properties of Oxides of Lanthanum, Neodymium and Samarium obtained by Solid State Decomposition of Nitrates. Part-I

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The catalytic activities of non-stoichiometric oxides of La, Nd, and Sm for the decomposition of H_2O_2 have been reported, indicating a decrease of catalytic activity of the oxides in the sequence, $La > Nd > Sm$. The mechanism of the decomposition of H_2O_2 has been discussed in the light of radical chain process. Magnetic susceptibility and electrical conductivity have also been measured. Oxides are found to be insulators and electrical conductivity have been discussed in terms of small polarons in 5d band and bound small polarons.

RARE earth compounds have been a subject of considerable interest in recent years^{1,2}. The catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide using lanthanides have been carried out^{3,4}, showing that the catalytic activity of the lanthanide decreases with increase of atomic numbers. This paper deals with a study of the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by non-stoichiometric oxides of La, Nd and Sm. Electrical conductivity and magnetic susceptibility have also been determined to get an idea of the nature and the environment of the metal atoms in the catalyst.

Experimental

Nitrates of La, Nd and Sm (Indian Rare Earth Ltd.), and H_2O_2 (G.R., Sarabhai) were used as such.

Preparation of sample: The method of preparation of the sample was essentially the same as described earlier⁵. The decomposition of nitrates of La, Nd, and Sm was carried out in a silica tube closed at one end and connected to a simple vacuum

system. The sample (5-10 g) was heated at 3° min^{-1} with the pump on, and the desired temperature was maintained for 1 h after which the sample was allowed to cool down to room temperature under the running reduced pressure. It was then grounded in agate mortar, sieved to 100 mesh (B.S.S.) and stored in a vacuum desiccator.

H_2O_2 decomposition: The decomposition of H_2O_2 was studied according to the reported procedure^{6,7}. The reaction was studied in the acidic medium (pH 4.5) at three different temperature, viz. 30° , 40° and 50° . The results are shown in Table 1.

Determination of metals in sample: The metals in oxides were estimated according to the reported procedure⁸. Empirical formulae were derived (Table 2).

Magnetic susceptibility: The magnetic susceptibility of different samples was determined with a Gouy magnetic balance. The compounds were found to be paramagnetic (Table 2). Except oxides from lanthanum nitrate all other oxides are para-

TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA FOR DECOMPOSITION OF 0.5% H_2O_2 IN PRESENCE OF OXIDE SAMPLES

Oxide samples from	Decomp. temp. °C	Specific rate ($\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at			E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	Log ₁₀ A
		30°	40°	50°		
La-nitrate	600	2.600	4.398	6.600	10.054	7.620
	700	0.520	1.600	3.640	19.010	14.060
	800	0.320	0.829	2.5.0	23.718	17.850
	960	0.527	1.070	2.256	12.970	9.600
Nd-nitrate	600	0.170	0.570	1.999	27.800	20.500
	700	0.120	0.324	0.850	19.460	14.070
	800	0.138	0.620	5.20	36.560	26.530
	960	0.142	0.414	1.252	23.910	17.370
Sm-nitrate	600	0.262	0.499	0.967	14.048	10.460
	700	—	0.115	0.170	—	—
	800	—	—	—	—	—
	960	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF OXIDE SAMPLES

Oxides from	Decomp. temp. °C	Magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^6$ erg g ⁻¹	Sp. conduc-tivity at 873 K Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	Empirical formula
La-nitrate	600	1.172	1.18×10^{-10}	LaO _{1.006}
	700	-0.323	7.31×10^{-11}	LaO _{0.790}
	800	0.256	6.29×10^{-11}	LaO _{1.738}
	960	0.067	8.82×10^{-11}	LaO _{1.530}
Nd-nitrate	600	30.800	9.8×10^{-11}	NdO _{2.580}
	700	22.700	8.5×10^{-11}	NdO _{1.580}
	800	25.480	8.0×10^{-11}	NdO _{0.570}
	960	36.600	9.4×10^{-11}	NdO _{0.769}
Sm-nitrate	600	5.900	3.3×10^{-10}	SmO _{1.640}
	700	5.380	1.1×10^{-10}	SmO _{1.610}
	800	5.410	4.2×10^{-10}	SmO _{1.599}
	960	9.500	2.6×10^{-10}	SmO _{0.809}

magnetic. The measurements were done at 5A, field strength 5.945×10^8 gauss.

Electrical conductivity : For the measurement of electric conductivity (σ), powdered specimens were pelleted into a disc of 1.299 cm dia and 0.10 to 0.20 cm thickness at uniform pressure of 8 ton/inch² using a metallic die and an electrically operated hydraulic press. The pellet after coating with conducting silver paint was held between two silver electrodes of suitable size and then placed into a furnace. The current was measured by Philips GB 6020 D.C. microvoltmeter having one megaohm input resistance. Electrostatic H.T. voltage stabiliser was used to apply electric field to the sample. From the known value of current (I), applied voltage (V) and dimension of the pellet, the electrical conductivity (σ) was calculated at different temperatures, using the relation,

$$\sigma = \frac{I L}{V A} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

where, A=area of pellet and L=thickness of pellet.

Results and Discussion

The first order rate curve for the decomposition of H₂O₂ on Nd-oxide sample is shown in Fig. 1. The decomposition of H₂O₂ on other oxide samples also follows the first order. The rate constants, energy of activation and frequency factors, calculated from the initial slopes of the rate curves, are given in Table 1.

A perusal of these values shows that the rate constant decreases steadily with the increase of atomic number of the lanthanide, indicating a decrease of the catalytic activity of the oxides in the sequence, La > Nd > Sm. The similar conclusion regarding the catalytic activity of the lanthanides for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been drawn³. It is also obvious that these oxides become progressively inactive for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide as the temperature of decomposition is increased. In the case of oxides prepared

Fig. 1. First order plot for decomposition of H₂O₂ on oxide samples at 30°: (○) La-oxide, (●) Nd-oxide and (×) Sm-oxide.

from neodymium nitrate the change of pattern of activation energy is not very regular but catalytic activity shows the same pattern as in the case of lanthanum oxides. The values of specific rate constant for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in the case of oxides of lanthanum are much less as compared to that of cobalt⁵ and these are still less in case of Nd, though the method of preparation of the catalyst is the same. This shows that d-electrons are more easily available than the f-electrons.

The compositions of the different samples of oxides obtained at different temperatures are given in Table 2. The results show that oxygen content in the sample decreases steadily as the temperature of decomposition increases. This indicates that in the present investigation, the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ is related with the nature of surface oxygen. The oxides from samarium nitrate prepared at 600 and 700° only show little catalytic activity for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. The oxides prepared at 800 and 960° from samarium nitrate do not show catalytic activity at all. It is obvious that the oxides prepared at 600° are catalytically most active for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. This leads to the idea that catalytic activity of the oxides may well be correlated with the higher concentrations of traps, i.e. with the larger deviations from stoichiometry in the direction of O-content. However, further study is needed to corroborate the observations.

Effect of pH on decomposition of H₂O₂ : Typical results depicting the variation of rate constants with change in pH values of medium are shown in Fig. 2. It is worthwhile to note that at around pH 7 the rate constant has the minimum value indicating that the decomposition proceeds at the slowest rate.

Mechanism of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide on oxides : It was found (Fig. 2) that irrespective of the composition of oxide samples, the decom-

Fig. 2. Decomposition of 0.5% H₂O₂ in different medium : (●) La-oxide from nitrate at 600° and (○) La-oxide from nitrate at 700°.

position is rapid both in acidic and alkaline media; the mechanism of decomposition may differ in two media. For the elucidation of mechanism of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide the possible involvement of radical chain process was ascertained. For the detection of the radical chain processes, in general and that of OH, in particular which might be formed as intermediates, the method of competing reactions was employed^{9,10}. Benzene and *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-nitrosoaniline were used as acceptors of hydroxy radicals. In the presence of benzene there was retardation in the rate of evolution of oxygen indicating the presence of radical chain process. Further, the presence of a stage involving the formation of hydroxy radicals under these conditions cannot be ruled out. In the light of the above views, the mechanism of decompositions in two media may be depicted as below.

In acidic medium :

In alkaline medium :

Thus, in our system there is a very likelihood of the decomposition of H₂O₂ through the intermediate formation of H₂Ö and with partial retentions of O-O bond in the evolved oxygen¹¹, probably in the fraction of 59 to 76%.

Induction period : When the first order plots were made with the experimental data it was observed that there was no linearity in the initial stages of the reaction (Fig. 1). Similar observations have been reported elsewhere^{12,13}. The cause of this induction period has been attributed to the retention of oxygen wholly or partially by the catalyst. In the case of rare earth magnetite, partial retention of oxygen has been experimentally verified. In our systems, the partial uptake of oxygen seems to be a time dependent process till it reaches equilibrium. Surface coverage is most probable. Probably during the induction period the reversible combination of oxygen and the catalyst occurs in the following sequence.

The molecules seem to act like an efficient O₂-carrier as in the case of globin in hemoglobin and thus step (2) is prevented after the attainment of the induction period. The low dielectric constant hinders the charge separation.

Magnetic susceptibility : The values of magnetic susceptibility are given in Table 2. Samples prepared from lanthanum nitrate seem to be diamagnetic, whereas samples from neodymium and samarium nitrates are paramagnetic. Our values of magnetic susceptibility are in agreement with those determined by others¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Practically there is no change in magnetic susceptibility in these samples with the change in temperature of decomposition. This may be attributed to the fact that there is no d-orbitals in oxygen available for pairing. From Table 2 it is also obvious that magnetic susceptibility decreases with the decrease in oxygen content of the sample except in the case of samarium oxide prepared at 960°. This observation supports the views that magnetic properties of europium and samarium ions are unique among the rare earths^{17,18}, they do not obey Hund's rule and the usual Currie-Weiss law¹⁹.

Electrical conductivity : The variation of log σ vs 10³/T in the temperature range 373-873 K for neodymium oxide samples is shown in Fig. 3. Similar curves have also been observed in case of lanthanum and samarium oxide samples. A look on the curves indicates two distinct temperature regions. Above 633 K the conductivity increases with increase of temperature (E_a = 1.287 eV) for neodymium oxide obtained at 960°, indicating semi-conducting behaviour. The conductivity values remain more or less unchanged below 633 K. Usually the conductivity data in solids are explained in terms of band theory¹⁹ with appropriate scattering mechanism. The relevant bands in these solids are M³⁺ (La³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺) : 5d band ; filled O²⁻ : 2P band ; and narrow M³⁺ : 4f band. M³⁺ : 5d band

Fig. 3. Electrical conductivity plot for neodymium oxides from nitrates: at (○) 600, (●) 700, (×) 800 and (□) 960°.

is the conduction band of the solid²⁰ and O²⁻ band is the valence band. The 5d band is a narrow band (1 eV wide at room temperature) and an electron in this band would form small or intermediate polarons (holes) with small mobility. Thus, the conductivity in this solid may probably be dominated by polarons. As the charge transport excitation of electron from the valence O²⁻(2P band) to cation M³⁺ (5d band) is expected to be of the order 3 eV at normal temperature, our samples are good insulators. The conductivity data in the temperature range 633-923 K can be expressed by the relation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_g/2kT) \quad (1)$$

With $E_g = 2.56$ eV for neodymium oxide obtained at 960° this value agrees reasonably well with that found by Pratap and Verma²¹.

More or less, below temperature 633 K, the conductivity remains constant. As our samples are

prepared by solid state decomposition, imperfections of different nature may be expected. This would lead to the presence of numerous isolated traps. In equilibrium at absolute zero, all the trap electrons would be in the deep traps. Below 633 K there may be strong interaction of trapped electrons with cations leading to the probable formation of small polarons, since the energy of activation E_a is 0.05 eV. The conductivity does not change with increase of temperature in these ranges. The plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $T^{-1/4}$ below 633 K has been found to be linear in the temperature range 373-633 K, indicating variation of conductivity according to Mott's law,

$$\sigma = C \exp\left(\frac{-B}{T^{1/4}}\right)$$

The values of C and B have been calculated to be $1.121 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $52.62 (T^{1/4})$, respectively.

This also suggests that randomly distributed localised impurities are responsible for the conduction *via* variable range hopping mechanism. The E_a values for conductance in case of other oxide samples obtained at different temperatures have also been calculated and it was observed that the E_a value for conductance decreases with the decrease in size of the cation. It is to be noted that the catalytic activity of the oxide samples for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide also decreases with the decrease in size of the cation. Thus, there appears some simple relation between activity and conductivity.

The Seebeck coefficient (α) measurement shows LaO_{1.728}, LaO_{1.580}, NdO_{2.580}, NdO_{1.880}, SmO_{1.640}, SmO_{1.610} and SmO_{1.590} to be n-type, and LaO_{1.006}, LaO_{0.780}, NdO_{0.570}, NdO_{0.760} and SmO_{0.600} to be p-type.

Compensation effect: The compensation effect (*i.e.* a relation between A and E of the form $\log A = E/a + b$) is also observed in our investigation and is depicted in Fig. 4. The occurrence of compensation effect for the hydrogen peroxide decom-

Fig. 4. $\log_{10} A$ as a function of activation energy of oxides samples; (○) La-oxides and (●) Nd-oxides.

position by lanthanon oxides might be due to the distribution of catalytic sites on the surface. Our method of preparations of sample is similar to that of Bhagat and Ahuja⁵ who decomposed H₂O₃ on the cobalt oxides surface obtained from the solid state decomposition of nitrates.

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